

ANALYSIS OF OPERATIVE AND TECHNOLOGICAL CONTEXT

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Executive Summary

This document is the deliverable “D2.1 – Analysis of operative and technological context” of the Horizon Europe project “eCREAM enabling Clinical Research in Emergency and Acute care Medicine through automated data extraction” (hereinafter also referred to as “eCREAM”, project number: 101057726).

This document outlines the necessary elements to set up the data extraction module, which is a goal of Work Package 2, and includes information on the purpose of this activity, as well as the stakeholders involved. Details are provided on what needs to be done in order to successfully complete the task.

The operational context analysis found that there is wide variability between different centers and between countries. At the center level, this can be an asset and a possible obstacle, since it will allow the team to work in different contexts, but will require certain parts of the work to be center-specific instead of generalizable to all centers. In general, the heterogeneity between centers and countries is one of the biggest obstacles in the eCREAM project. It is also one of the aspects on which we are placing the most effort in this phase of the project.

The technological context analysis found that the eCREAM platform will need to provide a common application programming interface (API) set for almost all the EHRs, but the lack of interoperability of a few ED EHRs will probably require the implementation of specific interface solutions. The analysis also found that the data that the eCREAM platform will receive will generally fit the required specifications, but a specific module for the transformation of data that are not consistent will need to be developed.

Concerning the data that will need to be processed for Use Cases 1 and 2, the major critical issues appear to be related to the information contained in the free text, especially that contained in the radiology test reports, available as PDF files. The eCREAM platform will therefore need to include a module that converts PDF files into text string data before the NLP algorithm processes it. Moreover, the NLP algorithm will have to be trained to infer structured data from the radiology reports.

The final conclusion that was drawn from the analysis is that, with the same amount of effort the eCREAM platform could gather information from a greater number of hospitals, which would be especially significant for the citizens’ mobile application.

Objectives of the WP2

WP2 aims to develop and validate the data extraction tool to retrieve the required information from the ED health records (both the EHRs in use and the new ED-EHR), other hospital patient records (such as the laboratory test results), and administrative databases.

More specifically, the objectives of WP2 include:

- analysing the operational and technological context where the participating EDs operate;
- mapping the essential data to address the Use Cases described in Pillar 4 and WP4 with the information available in both the EHRs in use and the new ED-EHR;
- developing and testing the modules interfacing with the eCREAM database and hospital systems.

Analysis of the operational context

The operational context of the EDs involved in the project has been analysed, specifically by:

1. assessing the structural and organisational resources operating in the EDs;
2. evaluating the regulations and underpinning legal framework of the EDs involved in the project, to determine the organisational model of the resources and operational scheme of the provided diagnostic-clinical-assistance pathways;
3. reviewing the hospital information systems used in the participating EDs, analysing the methodologies used to fill in data and the semantics of each collected piece of information;
4. reviewing country-specific data-sharing regulations applying to personal data.

In order to reach the first goal of this task, the IRFMN set up a web-based questionnaire to collect structural and organisational characteristics of the EDs involved in the project. The results of this survey are provided in Annex 1.

A total of 14 centers replied to the questionnaires: 13 to the ED part and 6 to the hospital part. The imbalance is due to the fact that the hospital-related part of the questionnaire was prepared after the ED part. One center replied to the hospital-related part but not yet to the ED-related one. We are continuing to collect data from the centers.

Thanks to this survey, it is possible to state that there is wide variability between different centers. This variability is, both, an asset to the eCREAM project, because it will allow us to work in different contexts, and a possible obstacle, since we will not be able to generalize some of the tasks to all the centers, but will need to work on an individual level.

Regarding goals 2 to 4 of this task, the ECRIN partner developed a specific questionnaire for the partners that addressed operational and legal issues related to the data processing activities in order to determine the legal requirements and legal risks. The questionnaire addressed operational and legal issues (e.g., categories of personal data, data flows, data transfer, legal and regulatory constraints: legal basis, regulatory submission, etc.).

Replies from partners are still being collected. From the few replies received so far, differences between centers have emerged.

In general, the results that emerged from the two questionnaires related to the analysis of operational context highlight heterogeneity between centers and between countries. This variation is one of the biggest obstacles in the eCREAM project. It is also one of the aspects on which we are placing the most effort in this phase of the project.

Analysis of the technological context

Data collection

The analysis of the EHRs involved in the eCREAM project and of their potential interoperability with the eCREAM platforms aims to allow the platform designers to answer these questions:

1. is there the need to develop any custom eCREAM interfaces for the interoperability of specific EDs (and with which technologies), or can all the EDs access an eCREAM interface set that is the same for all of them?
2. is the information needed to respond to the WP4 Use Case 1 and Use Case 2 purposes available in the EDs' data collections?

In order to collect information from the hospitals about the technological assets of their ED, Astir prepared two questionnaires, one on the ED software programs and one on the ED data collection:

- a Google web form (see Annex 2) that had the aim to collect information about:
 - software used in the ED: general information, technologies used, main functionalities, integration with other departmental software;
 - data and report storage infrastructures;
 - details on integration capabilities, FAIRification of data and any already running integration with non-hospital software;
 - contacts of IT staff for further analysis;
- an Excel form (see Annex 3) that had the aim of collecting information about the
 - format and coding of the data collected by the hospital information systems;
 - metadata available for each piece of information collected in the hospital systems;
 - timing needed for the availability of the single data items.

The Excel form was intended to examine these details with respect to a data set, defined with the supervision of IRFMN, that was designed as a first draft of the data set that eCREAM would need to gather from the EDs in order to perform the Use Case 1 (Analysis of the disposition decision to hospitalise a patient from the ED) and Use Case 2 (Development of a multipurpose dashboard to real-time inform end-users about predefined characteristics of the EDs), which are the goals of WP4.

The data set, which can be seen in its entirety in Annex 4, is composed of information about the following aspects of emergency case management in an ED:

- Patient arrival at the ED
- Triage
- Re-evaluation of the priority level
- Time-dependent disease
- Treatment
- Laboratory tests list
- Radiology exams
- Specialist consultancy
- Procedures (specific surgical, medical, or diagnostic interventions)
- Pharmaceutical therapy
- Respiratory support
- Vital signs monitoring
- Discharge decision
- Discharge

Observation unit

- Laboratory exams
- Radiology exams
- Specialist consultancy
- Procedures (specific surgical, medical, or diagnostic interventions)
- Pharmaceutical therapy
- Respiratory support
- Vital signs monitoring
- Discharge decision
- Discharge
- Observation Unit management

The questionnaires were sent to all the hospitals involved in the eCREAM project, except for 6 Italian hospitals already engaged in other data flow services that include similar information, and for the 4 Greek hospitals, which have no ED EHR software.

A meeting was organized with all the hospitals, with the participation of their ED and IT staff, to explain the questions included in the forms and provide support for the answers.

The results described in this chapter refer to the information collected at the end of August 2023. As of this date, Astir has received:

- the filled-out web form questionnaire from 13 hospitals;
- the filled-out Excel questionnaire from 13 hospitals.

This information was completed with data on 6 hospitals involved in Italian projects (EUOL – Lombardy Region, SmartEUS –Sicily Region) requiring their ED software to be integrated with a central data hub.

Similar information on which software (SW) is used was gathered in other 6 hospitals registered in the Fenice group, an Italian collaboration network of Emergency Departments that involves all the Italian eCREAM hospitals.

Currently, the information we have collected regards at least one hospital for each country involved in the project except Greece, because the Cretan hospitals don't use an EHR yet, and Poland, which is still collecting the required information. Table 1 lists the participant Hospitals and the source of the information collected for the context analysis:

Hospital or health organization name	Country	Web form	Excel	Fenice	Other projects
Santa Maria delle Grazie Hospital - Pozzuoli	Italy	X	X		
Ospedale Maggiore Carlo Alberto Pizzardi - Bologna	Italy		X	X	
ASUFC - Azienda Sanitaria Universitaria Friuli Centrale	Italy	X			
San Martino - Genova	Italy			X	
Papa Giovanni XXIII - Bergamo	Italy				X
ASST Sacco - Milano	Italy				X
Policlinico Ospedale Maggiore - Milano	Italy				X
ASST Grande H Metropolitan Niguarda - Milano	Italy				X
Ospedale di Circolo e Fondazione Macchi - Varese	Italy				X
AO SS. Antonio e Biagio e C. Arrigo - Alessandria	Italy	X	X		
AOU San Luigi Gonzaga - Orbassano	Italy	X	X		
Ospedale degli Infermi - Rivoli	Italy			X	
Ospedale San Giovanni Bosco - Torino	Italy	X	X		
ASL Vercelli	Italy	X	X		
AOUP "G. Rodolico - San Marco" . Catania	Italy				X
Ospedale Santa Maria Annunziata - Firenze	Italy	X	X		
Azienda ospedaliera di Perugia	Italy			X	
L. Pasteur University Hospital (UNLP 1)	Slovakia	X	X		
L. Pasteur University Hospital (UNLP 2)	Slovakia	X	X		
East Slovakia Institute of cardiovascular diseases - VUSCH	Slovakia	X	X		
AGEL Hospital	Slovakia	X	X		
Univerzitetni klinicni center Maribor	Slovenia	X	X		
Royal Surrey County Hospital	UK				X
Ashford and St Peter's hospitals NHS foundation trust	UK	X	X		

Table 1 – list of healthcare organizations that have provided information used in the analysis

Results concerning ED SW and their interoperability potentialities

The table shows that 16 different ED software programs were counted in 24 hospital facilities (some serve more than one ED).

SWH	SW	Country	Served hospitals
Cerner	Cerner ED SW	UK	2
CID Software	Prime PS	Italy	1
Datalan	Ordinis	Slovakia	1
Dedalus	FirstAid	Italy	4
Dedalus	HERO	Italy	1
Engineering	AREAS/PSweb	Italy	2
GPI	NGH PS	Italy	2
GPI	Opera	Italy	1
Hi.Tech	PS3	Italy	1
Hi.Tech	PSNet	Italy	1
Infonet	Medis	Slovenia	1
INSIEL	SEI	Italy	1
Intersystems	TrackCare	Italy	2
LCS	KNIS	Slovakia	2
Prosoft Kosice	Promis	Slovakia	1
S3K	jHIS	Italy	1

Table 2 – list of software programs used in eCREAM hospitals

Analysing the web form questionnaire and the other sources, we know that:

1. the EHR infrastructure can be hosted within or outside the hospital facilities:
 - in a cloud server farm for 1 hospital
 - in the hospital server farm for 17 hospitals
2. the same infrastructure can serve one or more hospitals:
 - only 1 ED in 5 cases
 - more than 1 ED in the same hospital administrative group in 13 cases

This information is important in case eCREAM will design some of its services for a wider list of hospitals than the ones directly participating in the project.

3. For all the hospitals, laboratory results are available in ED, by integration with the Laboratory Information System (LIS), in a PDF file. Hospital document repository and LIS can provide the results in structured data format.
4. For all the hospitals, radiology results are available in ED, by integration with the Radiology Information System (RIS), in a PDF file. Hospital document repository and RIS can provide the results in structured data format.
5. The Observation Unit data collection is a part of the whole EHR data collection for all the EDs.

6. The question about the technologies that are already being used for the interoperability of the ED EHR had these answers:
 - DB synchronization, in 1 case
 - custom web service interface (e.g., REST or SOAP), in 14 cases
 - HL7 in 8 cases
 - HL7 FHIR in 8 cases, mostly for integration with LIS and RIS
7. 11 hospitals have already implemented a data flow from the ED EHR to an application for citizens, to show them information about the number of patients waiting and the number being visited in their ED.
8. Some EHRs simultaneously serve a group of EDs, so it is possible that, with the integration of such an EHR, the eCREAM platform can gather information from more than one ED at the same time. This is true for these hospitals:

eCREAM hospitals that use the EHR	Number of other EDs using the same EHR
Ospedale Santa Maria Annunziata - AUSL Toscana centro	12
Ospedale Udine - Azienda Sanitaria Universitaria Friuli Centrale	10
Ospedale di Circolo e Fondazione Macchi – ASST 7 Laghi	5
Santa Maria delle Grazie - ASL Napoli 2 Nord	4
Ospedale di Alessandria – AO di Alessandria	4
Ospedale San Giovanni Bosco – ASL "Città di Torino"	2
Ospedale di Vercelli – ASL di Vercelli	1
Ospedale Sacco di Milano – ASST Fatebenefratelli Sacco	1
Ospedale Papa Giovanni XXIII - ASST Papa Giovanni XXIII	1
Ospedale G. Rodolico - AOUP "G. Rodolico - San Marco" di Catania	1

This is very useful information in order to design and provide the mobile app for citizens, which is a goal of the WP4, Use Case 2.

Results concerning ED data collection

Data availability

The Excel questionnaire required that, for each data item in a draft dataset, the hospital would register if, in the ED's electronic database, it was:

- available
- available as proxy information (available with some difference in the specification)
- not available at all

The less available information, ordered by type, is:

Patient arrival at the ED

- Pre-hospital emergency service Operations Center (in case of arrival by ambulance/helicopter) Identification code of the Operations Center that managed the mission when the patient arrived at the ED transported by ambulance/helicopter dispatched by a Pre-hospital emergency service Operations Center
- Patient’s access identification code in the previous ED, in case of patient arrived at the ED with a transfer from another hospital.

Not available in **37%** of the EDs

Not available in **58%** of the EDs

Time-dependent disease

- Time at which a nurse or a clinician registers that the patient must be assisted and cared for by observing a protocol specific to a time-dependent disease

Not available in **42%** of the EDs

ED Treatment

- Vital signs monitoring, date and time of end

Not available in **32%** of the EDs

Observation Unit Treatment

- Respiratory support, date and time of start
- Respiratory support, date and time of end
- Vital signs monitoring, date and time of start
- Vital signs monitoring, date and time of end

Not available in **32%** of the EDs

Not available in **37%** of the EDs

Not available in **32%** of the EDs

Not available in **42%** of the EDs

Observation Unit Discharge decision

- Type of hospital admission unit/department, in case of planned hospitalization: ordinary, semi-intensive or intensive bed

Not available in **32%** of the EDs

The WP4 board will evaluate if this information is crucial for the experimental Use Cases and if an organizational and/or a software solution needs to be developed in order to obtain it.

All the other information is available in at least 70% of the hospitals.

The complete table of the percentage for each data item is provided in Annex 4.

Concerning the uniformity of the available information among the ED collections, the data that, when available, most frequently differ from the proposed definition are:

ED Treatment

- Laboratory test, date and time of execution
- Radiology test, date and time of execution

Not available in **37%** of the EDs

Not available in **42%** of the EDs

Observation Unit Treatment

- Laboratory test, date and time of execution
- Radiology test, date and time of execution

Not available in **37%** of the EDs

Not available in **37%** of the EDs

Data format

The Excel questionnaire required that, for each available data item, the hospital would register if the ED EHR stores it as:

- Structured data
- Free text

Structured data can be used directly and be elaborated without pre-processing, while free text must be elaborated, for WP4 purposes, only after processing it with NLP algorithms.

Moreover, the input and storage of structured data can be controlled more easily, and the data quality is therefore usually higher.

The information that is more commonly registered as free text in the EDs (excluding specialists' and ED physicians' notes) ordered by type, is:

ED Treatment

- Respiratory support, date and time of start
- Respiratory support, date and time of end
- Vital signs monitoring, date and time of start
- Vital signs monitoring, date and time of end

In free text in **44%** of the EDs

In free text in **44%** of the EDs

In free text in **35%** of the EDs

In free text in **33%** of the EDs

Discharge

- Patient's severity level as evaluated by the physician at discharge

In free text in **31%** of the EDs

Observation Unit Treatment

- Respiratory support, date and time of start
- Respiratory support, date and time of end
- Vital signs monitoring, date and time of start
- Vital signs monitoring, date and time of end

In free text in **43%** of the EDs

In free text in **43%** of the EDs

In free text in **33%** of the EDs

In free text in **31%** of the EDs

Conclusions on the technological context

In order to answer the question of whether all the EDs can access an eCREAM interface that is the same for all of them, the analysis of the ED EHR software reveals that:

- there is a considerable variety of software to deal with, even in the same country
- almost all the EHRs seem to use the technologies that allow the software houses or the hospital IT teams to develop a web service client according to specifications that are the same for all, but:
 - there is at least 1 ED whose EHR seems not to fit these technological requirements
 - not all the hospitals involved in the project have sent the information regarding their ED EHR yet
- when available, the required ED information definitions are generally consistent among the EDs, so that they need few transformations, or none at all, before the ED software sends the data to the eCREAM platform

This evidence leads to these conclusions:

- the eCREAM platform will have to provide a common application programming interface (API) set for almost all the EHRs, but some specific interface solutions will probably have to be implemented to compensate for the lack of interoperability of a few ED EHRs
- the eCREAM platform will receive data that are generally consistent with the required specifications, but a specific module for the transformation of data that are not consistent, and that the ED software is not able to transform before sending, needs to be developed

Concerning the availability of the requested information, as far as we know at this phase of the project about which data will need to be processed for Use Cases 1 and 2, the major critical issues appear to be related to the relevant information contained in free text. This is especially true for the information contained in the radiology test reports, which are available as PDF files.

For these reasons, the eCREAM platform must include a module that converts PDF files into text string data before the NLP algorithm processes it. Such a module will be the subject of future development and will be described in a future report. Moreover, the NLP algorithm will have to be trained to infer structured data from the radiology reports.

The last conclusion that we can draw from the analysis is that, at least for the WP4 Use Case 2, with the same amount of effort the eCREAM platform could gather information from a greater number of hospitals located in a broader area than that of the hospitals participating directly in the project. This could be especially significant for the citizens' mobile application, whose importance increases in parallel with the size of the population served.

Structural data report

1 Participation

Total number of participant centers: 14

2 Hospital

Number of centers with hospital data: 6

2.1 Organization

2.1.1 Structure and organisation of the hospital

	All centers (N=6)
Functioning hospital beds	
Mean (SD)	550 (357)
Median (Q1, Q3)	443 (282, 726)
Missing	0
Hospitals	
	All centers (N=6)
Number of hospitals	
Mean (SD)	1.3 (0.5)
Median (Q1, Q3)	1.0 (1.0, 1.8)
Missing	0
More than one hospital	2 (33.3%)
Dedicated transp. service for pts. with time-dep. diseases	1 (50.0%)
Dedicated transp. service for ordinary adm./consultations	1 (50.0%)
Logistics of the hospital	
	All centers (N=6)
Pavilions	2 (33.3%)
Dedicated transport service for patients	2 (100.0%)
Helipad	
	All centers (N=6)
Helipad present	4 (66.7%)
Possibility of night flights	1 (25.0%)
Bed manager	
	All centers (N=6)
Bed manager	5 (83.3%)
Profession	
Nurse	5 (100.0%)
Doctor	0 (0.0%)
Administrative employee	0 (0.0%)
Affiliation	
ED	0 (0.0%)
Hospital administration services	4 (80.0%)
Other	1 (20.0%)
Active morning weekdays	5 (100.0%)
Active afternoon weekdays	5 (100.0%)
Active night weekdays	0 (0.0%)
Active morning holidays	2 (40.0%)
Active afternoon holidays	1 (20.0%)
Active night holidays	0 (0.0%)

2.2 Specialties

2.2.1 Medical area

Independent departments available	All centers (N=6)
Internal medicine	6 (100.0%)
In dedicated department	6 (100.0%)
Total working beds (dedicated department)	
Mean (SD)	66.0 (49.3)
Median (Q1, Q3)	45.0 (31.5, 88.5)
Missing	0
Emergency medicine	5 (83.3%)
In dedicated department	5 (100.0%)
Total working beds (dedicated department)	
Mean (SD)	21.4 (10.7)
Median (Q1, Q3)	24.0 (14.0, 29.0)
Missing	0

Independent departments available	All centers (N=6)
Intensive care unit	6 (100.0%)
In dedicated department	6 (100.0%)
Total working beds (dedicated department)	
Mean (SD)	19.7 (13.0)
Median (Q1, Q3)	13.0 (11.2, 27.5)
Missing	0
Cardiology	6 (100.0%)
In dedicated department	6 (100.0%)
Total working beds (dedicated department)	
Mean (SD)	28.2 (15.3)
Median (Q1, Q3)	20.5 (20.0, 32.2)
Missing	0
Neurology	6 (100.0%)
In dedicated department	6 (100.0%)
Total working beds (dedicated department)	
Mean (SD)	27.5 (24.7)
Median (Q1, Q3)	19.5 (15.0, 28.5)
Missing	0
Psychiatry	6 (100.0%)
In dedicated department	6 (100.0%)
Total working beds (dedicated department)	
Mean (SD)	30.3 (39.1)
Median (Q1, Q3)	16.0 (13.0, 16.0)
Missing	0
Pneumology	4 (66.7%)
In dedicated department	4 (100.0%)
Total working beds (dedicated department)	
Mean (SD)	32.0 (7.5)
Median (Q1, Q3)	32.5 (27.5, 37.0)
Missing	0
Nephrology	5 (83.3%)
In dedicated department	4 (80.0%)
Total working beds (dedicated department)	
Mean (SD)	17.2 (10.3)
Median (Q1, Q3)	18.0 (13.8, 21.5)
Missing	0
Infectious diseases	3 (50.0%)
In dedicated department	3 (100.0%)
Total working beds (dedicated department)	
Mean (SD)	27.0 (4.2)
Median (Q1, Q3)	27.0 (25.5, 28.5)
Missing	1
Gastroenterology	3 (50.0%)
In dedicated department	2 (66.7%)
Total working beds (dedicated department)	
Mean (SD)	17.5 (13.4)
Median (Q1, Q3)	17.5 (12.8, 22.2)
Missing	0
Rheumatology	3 (50.0%)
In dedicated department	2 (66.7%)
Total working beds (dedicated department)	
Mean (SD)	15.5 (19.1)
Median (Q1, Q3)	15.5 (8.8, 22.2)
Missing	0
Oncology	5 (83.3%)
In dedicated department	4 (80.0%)
Total working beds (dedicated department)	
Mean (SD)	18.0 (5.7)

Independent departments available	All centers (N=6)
Median (Q1, Q3)	20.0 (16.0, 22.0)
Missing	0
Haematology	4 (66.7%)
In dedicated department	4 (100.0%)
Total working beds (dedicated department)	
Mean (SD)	16.8 (5.1)
Median (Q1, Q3)	15.5 (14.2, 18.0)
Missing	0
Paediatrics	4 (66.7%)
In dedicated department	4 (100.0%)
Total working beds (dedicated department)	
Mean (SD)	29.2 (23.7)
Median (Q1, Q3)	23.0 (17.0, 35.2)
Missing	0
Rehabilitation	3 (50.0%)
In dedicated department	2 (66.7%)
Total working beds (dedicated department)	
Mean (SD)	60.0 (28.3)
Median (Q1, Q3)	60.0 (50.0, 70.0)
Missing	0
Subacute care	2 (33.3%)
In dedicated department	2 (100.0%)
Total working beds (dedicated department)	
Mean (SD)	17.5 (3.5)
Median (Q1, Q3)	17.5 (16.2, 18.8)
Missing	0
Hospice	1 (16.7%)
In dedicated department	1 (100.0%)
Total working beds (dedicated department)	
Mean (SD)	7.0 (NA)
Median (Q1, Q3)	7.0 (7.0, 7.0)
Missing	0

2.2.2 Specialist surgeries

Independent surgery wards available

Independent surgery wards available	All centers (N=6)
General surgery	6 (100.0%)
Location	
Dedicated department	6 (100.0%)
Beds in a polyspecialistic area	0 (0.0%)
Procedures only	0 (0.0%)
Total working beds (dedicated department)	
Mean (SD)	35.5 (22.2)
Median (Q1, Q3)	26.0 (21.8, 46.8)
Missing	0
Emergency surgery	0 (0.0%)
Neurosurgery	5 (83.3%)
Location	
Dedicated department	5 (100.0%)

Independent surgery wards available	All centers (N=6)
Beds in a polyspecialistic area	0 (0.0%)
Procedures only	0 (0.0%)
Total working beds (dedicated department)	
Mean (SD)	23.0 (5.7)
Median (Q1, Q3)	25.0 (18.0, 27.0)
Missing	0
Polytrauma surgery	0 (0.0%)
Thoracic surgery	5 (83.3%)
Location	
Dedicated department	4 (80.0%)
Beds in a polyspecialistic area	1 (20.0%)
Procedures only	0 (0.0%)
Total working beds (dedicated department)	
Mean (SD)	11.0 (9.0)
Median (Q1, Q3)	7.5 (5.0, 13.5)
Missing	0
Vascular surgery	4 (66.7%)
Location	
Dedicated department	3 (75.0%)
Beds in a polyspecialistic area	1 (25.0%)
Procedures only	0 (0.0%)
Total working beds (dedicated department)	
Mean (SD)	18.7 (4.7)
Median (Q1, Q3)	17.0 (16.0, 20.5)
Missing	0
Orthopaedics	6 (100.0%)
Location	
Dedicated department	6 (100.0%)
Beds in a polyspecialistic area	0 (0.0%)
Procedures only	0 (0.0%)
Total working beds (dedicated department)	
Mean (SD)	23.8 (11.1)
Median (Q1, Q3)	21.5 (17.2, 28.8)
Missing	0
Cardiosurgery	4 (66.7%)
Location	
Dedicated department	3 (75.0%)
Beds in a polyspecialistic area	1 (25.0%)
Procedures only	0 (0.0%)
Total working beds (dedicated department)	
Mean (SD)	21.3 (12.7)
Median (Q1, Q3)	19.0 (14.5, 27.0)
Missing	0
Otolaryngology	6 (100.0%)
Location	
Dedicated department	5 (83.3%)
Beds in a polyspecialistic area	1 (16.7%)
Procedures only	0 (0.0%)
Total working beds (dedicated department)	
Mean (SD)	14.6 (16.1)
Median (Q1, Q3)	8.0 (4.0, 16.0)
Missing	0
Urology	6 (100.0%)
Location	
Dedicated department	6 (100.0%)
Beds in a polyspecialistic area	0 (0.0%)
Procedures only	0 (0.0%)
Total working beds (dedicated department)	

Independent surgery wards available	All centers (N=6)
Mean (SD)	18.7 (7.9)
Median (Q1, Q3)	16.5 (15.0, 25.5)
Missing	0
Maxillofacial surgery	4 (66.7%)
Location	
Dedicated department	1 (25.0%)
Beds in a polyspecialistic area	3 (75.0%)
Procedures only	0 (0.0%)
Total working beds (dedicated department)	
Mean (SD)	7.0 (NA)
Median (Q1, Q3)	7.0 (7.0, 7.0)
Missing	0
Transplant surgery	0 (0.0%)
Gynaecology	4 (66.7%)
Location	
Dedicated department	4 (100.0%)
Beds in a polyspecialistic area	0 (0.0%)
Procedures only	0 (0.0%)
Total working beds (dedicated department)	
Mean (SD)	41.0 (28.2)
Median (Q1, Q3)	34.5 (24.0, 51.5)
Missing	0
Obstetrics	4 (66.7%)
Location	
Dedicated department	2 (50.0%)
Beds in a polyspecialistic area	2 (50.0%)
Procedures only	0 (0.0%)
Total working beds (dedicated department)	
Mean (SD)	35.5 (21.9)
Median (Q1, Q3)	35.5 (27.8, 43.2)
Missing	0
Paediatric surgery	2 (33.3%)
Location	
Dedicated department	1 (50.0%)
Beds in a polyspecialistic area	1 (50.0%)
Procedures only	0 (0.0%)
Total working beds (dedicated department)	
Mean (SD)	15.0 (NA)
Median (Q1, Q3)	15.0 (15.0, 15.0)
Missing	0

2.2.3 Intensive care units

Intensive care units available

Intensive care units available	All centers (N=6)
General (polyvalent)	5 (83.3%)
Number of units	
Mean (SD)	1.4 (0.9)
Median (Q1, Q3)	1.0 (1.0, 1.0)
Missing	0
Total number of beds	
Mean (SD)	16.8 (12.0)
Median (Q1, Q3)	12.0 (11.0, 14.0)
Missing	0
Number of beds with possibility of isolation	
Mean (SD)	4.2 (3.5)
Median (Q1, Q3)	4.0 (2.0, 4.0)
Missing	0
Medical	1 (16.7%)
Number of units	
Mean (SD)	1.0 (NA)
Median (Q1, Q3)	1.0 (1.0, 1.0)
Missing	0

Intensive care units available	All centers (N=6)
Total number of beds	
Mean (SD)	12.0 (NA)
Median (Q1, Q3)	12.0 (12.0, 12.0)
Missing	0
Number of beds with possibility of isolation	
Mean (SD)	2.0 (NA)
Median (Q1, Q3)	2.0 (2.0, 2.0)
Missing	0
General surgical	1 (16.7%)
Number of units	
Mean (SD)	1.0 (NA)
Median (Q1, Q3)	1.0 (1.0, 1.0)
Missing	0
Total number of beds	
Mean (SD)	15.0 (NA)
Median (Q1, Q3)	15.0 (15.0, 15.0)
Missing	0
Number of beds with possibility of isolation	
Mean (SD)	3.0 (NA)
Median (Q1, Q3)	3.0 (3.0, 3.0)
Missing	0
Neurological	0 (0.0%)
Cardiological	2 (33.3%)
Number of units	
Mean (SD)	1.0 (0.0)
Median (Q1, Q3)	1.0 (1.0, 1.0)
Missing	0
Total number of beds	
Mean (SD)	7.5 (0.7)
Median (Q1, Q3)	7.5 (7.2, 7.8)
Missing	0
Number of beds with possibility of isolation	
Mean (SD)	0.0 (0.0)
Median (Q1, Q3)	0.0 (0.0, 0.0)
Missing	0
Cardiosurgical	3 (50.0%)
Number of units	
Mean (SD)	1.0 (0.0)
Median (Q1, Q3)	1.0 (1.0, 1.0)
Missing	0
Total number of beds	
Mean (SD)	7.7 (2.1)
Median (Q1, Q3)	7.0 (6.5, 8.5)
Missing	0
Number of beds with possibility of isolation	
Mean (SD)	2.0 (2.8)
Median (Q1, Q3)	2.0 (1.0, 3.0)
Missing	1
Burns	0 (0.0%)
Post-transplantation	0 (0.0%)
Paediatric	2 (33.3%)
Number of units	
Mean (SD)	1.0 (0.0)
Median (Q1, Q3)	1.0 (1.0, 1.0)
Missing	0
Total number of beds	
Mean (SD)	7.0 (1.4)

	All centers (N=6)
Intensive care units available	
Median (Q1, Q3)	7.0 (6.5, 7.5)
Missing	0
Number of beds with possibility of isolation	
Mean (SD)	0.0 (NA)
Median (Q1, Q3)	0.0 (0.0, 0.0)
Missing	1
Neonatal	3 (50.0%)
Number of units	
Mean (SD)	1.0 (0.0)
Median (Q1, Q3)	1.0 (1.0, 1.0)
Missing	0
Total number of beds	
Mean (SD)	9.0 (3.6)
Median (Q1, Q3)	10.0 (7.5, 11.0)
Missing	0
Number of beds with possibility of isolation	
Mean (SD)	2.0 (2.8)
Median (Q1, Q3)	2.0 (1.0, 3.0)
Missing	1
Other intensive care units	1 (16.7%)

2.2.4 High dependency units / semintensive care units

	All centers (N=6)
Semintensive care units available	
General (polyvalent)	5 (83.3%)
Number of units	
Mean (SD)	1.0 (0.0)
Median (Q1, Q3)	1.0 (1.0, 1.0)
Missing	0
Total number of beds	
Mean (SD)	10.2 (2.8)
Median (Q1, Q3)	9.0 (9.0, 12.0)
Missing	0
Number of beds with possibility of isolation	
Mean (SD)	1.8 (1.3)
Median (Q1, Q3)	1.0 (1.0, 2.0)
Missing	0
General surgical	2 (33.3%)
Number of units	
Mean (SD)	1.0 (0.0)
Median (Q1, Q3)	1.0 (1.0, 1.0)
Missing	0
Total number of beds	
Mean (SD)	10.0 (2.8)
Median (Q1, Q3)	10.0 (9.0, 11.0)
Missing	0
Number of beds with possibility of isolation	
Mean (SD)	4.0 (5.7)
Median (Q1, Q3)	4.0 (2.0, 6.0)
Missing	0
Cardiological	3 (50.0%)
Number of units	
Mean (SD)	1.0 (0.0)
Median (Q1, Q3)	1.0 (1.0, 1.0)
Missing	0
Total number of beds	
Mean (SD)	8.0 (0.0)
Median (Q1, Q3)	8.0 (8.0, 8.0)
Missing	0
Number of beds with possibility of isolation	
Mean (SD)	2.3 (3.2)
Median (Q1, Q3)	1.0 (0.5, 3.5)
Missing	0
Neurological (stroke unit)	5 (83.3%)
Number of units	
Mean (SD)	1.0 (0.0)
Median (Q1, Q3)	1.0 (1.0, 1.0)
Missing	0
Total number of beds	
Mean (SD)	5.6 (1.7)
Median (Q1, Q3)	6.0 (4.0, 6.0)
Missing	0
Number of beds with possibility of isolation	
Mean (SD)	0.0 (0.0)
Median (Q1, Q3)	0.0 (0.0, 0.0)
Missing	1
Respiratory	2 (33.3%)
Number of units	
Mean (SD)	1.0 (0.0)
Median (Q1, Q3)	1.0 (1.0, 1.0)
Missing	0

Semintensive care units available	All centers (N=6)
Total number of beds	
Mean (SD)	8.0 (5.7)
Median (Q1, Q3)	8.0 (6.0, 10.0)
Missing	0
Number of beds with possibility of isolation	
Mean (SD)	2.5 (2.1)
Median (Q1, Q3)	2.5 (1.8, 3.2)
Missing	0
Other semintensive care units	2 (33.3%)

2.3 Services

2.3.1 Radiology

Radiology	All centers (N=6)
Conventional radiological reporting	6 (100.0%)
Available H24	6 (100.0%)
CT Body	6 (100.0%)
Available H24	6 (100.0%)
MRI Body	6 (100.0%)
Available H24	4 (66.7%)
CT Neuro	6 (100.0%)
Available H24	6 (100.0%)
MRI Neuro	6 (100.0%)
Available H24	5 (83.3%)
Neuroradiological reporting	5 (83.3%)
Available H24	1 (100.0%)
Interventional neuroradiology	4 (66.7%)
Available H24	4 (100.0%)
Interventional radiology	4 (66.7%)
Available H24	4 (100.0%)

2.3.2 General lab

General lab	All centers (N=6)
Laboratory	6 (100.0%)
Available H24	6 (100.0%)
Dedicated working line for the ED	4 (66.7%)
Reporting	
H24	4 (100.0%)
H12	0 (0.0%)
Less than H12	0 (0.0%)

2.3.3 Microbiology lab

Microbiology lab	All centers (N=6)
Laboratory	4 (66.7%)
Available H24	3 (75.0%)
Cultures processed H24	6 (100.0%)
Rapid tests for the identification of micro-organisms	5 (83.3%)

2.3.4 Other services

Other services	All centers (N=6)
Interventional haemodynamics	5 (83.3%)
Availability	
Available H24 (also on call)	5 (100.0%)
H12 with on call	0 (0.0%)
H12 without on call	0 (0.0%)
Less than H12	0 (0.0%)
Digestive endoscopy	6 (100.0%)
Available H24	6 (100.0%)
Bronchoscopy	5 (83.3%)
Available H24	5 (100.0%)
Hyperbaric chamber	0 (0.0%)
Blood transfusion centre	5 (83.3%)
Available H24	5 (100.0%)

2.4 Trauma model

2.4.1 Trauma organisational model

Trauma organisational model	All centers (N=6)
Sala op. e radiodiagnostica adiacenti al PS	0 (0.0%)
Trauma team	4 (66.7%)
Available H24	4 (100.0%)
Protocol for major trauma	6 (100.0%)
Protocol for massive transfusion	4 (66.7%)

Specialists included in the trauma team	All centers (N=4)
Surgeon	4 (100.0%)
Orthopaedist	3 (75.0%)
Radiologist	2 (50.0%)
Intensivist	4 (100.0%)
Emergency physician	4 (100.0%)
ED nurse	4 (100.0%)
Nurse from other divisions	1 (25.0%)
Radiology technician	2 (50.0%)
Other	1 (25.0%)

Resources available in the ED	All centers (N=6)
Pelvic stabiliser (e.g. T-POD)	6 (100.0%)
Radiotranslucent bed	6 (100.0%)
High-flux fluid heater (e.g. Level 1)	6 (100.0%)
High-flow vascular catheter	5 (83.3%)
At least 3 concentrated blood units	5 (83.3%)

3 ED

Number of centers with ED data: 13

3.1 General data

3.1.1 General characteristics

	All centers (N=13)
<hr/>	
Catchment area (last year)	
Median	345000
Q1, Q3	200000, 400000
Missing	0

	All centers (N=13)
<hr/>	
Hub center for one or more diseases	
No	0 (0.0%)
Yes	13 (100.0%)

Hub center

All centers
(N=13)

Number of diseases for which the center is HUB

0	0 (0.0%)
1	1 (7.7%)
2	1 (7.7%)
3	2 (15.4%)
4	2 (15.4%)
5	1 (7.7%)
6	6 (46.2%)

All centers
(N=13)

Number of yearly visits excluding fast track accesses (last year)

Mean (SD)	52156 (19417)
Median	56683
Q1, Q3	42524, 63052
Missing	1

Number of yearly visits (last year)

All centers (N=13)	
Fast track	
No	2 (15.4%)
Yes	11 (84.6%)
Fast track type	
All centers (N=13)	
Ophthalmology	8 (61.5%)
Yearly visits (last year)	
Mean (SD)	2401 (1555)
Median (Q1, Q3)	1738 (1355, 3319)
Missing	0
Otolaryngology	7 (53.8%)
Yearly visits (last year)	
Mean (SD)	989 (741)
Median (Q1, Q3)	789 (460, 1320)
Missing	0
Dermatological	1 (7.7%)
Yearly visits (last year)	
Mean (SD)	31 (NA)
Median (Q1, Q3)	31 (31, 31)
Missing	0
Orthopedic	6 (46.2%)
Yearly visits (last year)	
Mean (SD)	5655 (3088)
Median (Q1, Q3)	5602 (3544, 8004)
Missing	0
Psychiatric	3 (23.1%)
Yearly visits (last year)	
Mean (SD)	1268 (650)
Median (Q1, Q3)	1502 (1018, 1636)
Missing	0
Gynecological	5 (38.5%)
Yearly visits (last year)	
Mean (SD)	8147 (9468)
Median (Q1, Q3)	6078 (684, 13542)

Fast track type	All centers (N=13)
Missing	1
Other	1 (7.7%)

3.1.1.1 Patient statistics

Statistics (last year) - Percentage	All centers (N=13)
Patients discharged home from ED	
Mean (SD)	75.3 (14.5)
Median (Q1, Q3)	81.8 (69.7, 84.8)
Missing	4
Patients deceased in the ED	
Mean (SD)	0.4 (0.2)
Median (Q1, Q3)	0.3 (0.1, 0.6)
Missing	2
Patients hospitalized from the ED	
Mean (SD)	19.6 (6.4)
Median (Q1, Q3)	18.7 (14.8, 22.0)
Missing	3
Patients leaving without being seen	
Mean (SD)	5.6 (5.1)
Median (Q1, Q3)	4.2 (1.5, 10.3)
Missing	5
Patients leaving after the start of the visit	
Mean (SD)	3.0 (3.2)
Median (Q1, Q3)	1.7 (1.0, 4.2)
Missing	6

3.2 Triage and post triage

3.2.1 General characteristics

Triage	All centers (N=13)
Pediatric	7 (53.8%)
Managed separately from the general ED	3 (42.9%)
Gynecological	7 (53.8%)
Managed separately from the general ED	6 (85.7%)
Obstetric	7 (53.8%)
Managed separately from the general ED	6 (85.7%)
Trauma	4 (30.8%)
Managed separately from the general ED	0 (0.0%)
Infectious diseases	6 (46.2%)
Managed separately from the general ED	1 (16.7%)
Any other specialistic triage	1 (7.7%)
Managed separately from the general ED	0 (0.0%)

3.2.2 Spaces

Spaces	All centers (N=13)
Heated area right outside the entrance	10 (76.9%)
Ambulances in heated area	
Mean (SD)	2.8 (1.7)
Median (Q1, Q3)	2.0 (2.0, 3.8)
Missing	0
Decontamination area	11 (84.6%)
Administrative registration	7 (53.8%)
Dedicated area	6 (85.7%)
Performed 24/h day	4 (57.1%)
Separate paths for patients walking or on stretchers	9 (69.2%)

	All centers (N=13)
Spaces	
Triage performed in dedicated rooms	8 (61.5%)
Number of dedicated rooms	
Mean (SD)	1.9 (0.6)
Median (Q1, Q3)	2.0 (1.8, 2.0)
Missing	0
Negative pressure available	3 (37.5%)
Area to transfer patients from stretchers	8 (61.5%)
Pre-triage waiting area	7 (53.8%)
Spaces for the post-triage activities	8 (61.5%)
Rooms/cubicles for the initial medical assessment	5 (62.5%)
Waiting area for the relatives of patients	9 (69.2%)
Dedicated staff	3 (33.3%)
Screens for the wait management	7 (77.8%)
Toilets for waiting patients	13 (100.0%)
Video surveillance system	11 (84.6%)
Security service	10 (76.9%)

3.2.3 Resources and equipment

	All centers (N=13)
Resources	
System computer-based triage	11 (84.6%)
Number of computer workstations	
Mean (SD)	2.3 (1.1)
Median (Q1, Q3)	2.0 (2.0, 3.0)
Missing	0
Electrocardiographs or other equipment to perform ECGs	11 (84.6%)
Multi-parameter patient monitors available	11 (84.6%)
Backboard/mattress splints for spinal immobilisation	11 (84.6%)

	All centers (N=13)
Point of Care	
Blood gas analyzer	9 (69.2%)
Troponin	2 (15.4%)
Coagulation	2 (15.4%)
Ultrasound	11 (84.6%)
Blood glucose test (finger prick)	9 (69.2%)
None of the above	2 (15.4%)

3.2.4 Work organization

	All centers (N=13)
Triage system levels	
4	5 (38.5%)
5	7 (53.8%)
1	1 (7.7%)

	All centers (N=13)
Work organization	
Standardized triage protocols	12 (92.3%)
Patient identification systems	11 (84.6%)

Work organization	All centers (N=13)
Identification systems for relatives/caregivers of patients	5 (38.5%)
Triage organized as two-step triage	4 (30.8%)
Nurse-managed referral to outpatient care	1 (7.7%)

All centers (N=13)	
Nurse-initiated treatment protocol in place	
No	5 (38.5%)
Yes	8 (61.5%)

All centers (N=13)	
Number of nurse-initiated treatment protocols in place	
0	5 (38.5%)
1	2 (15.4%)
2	2 (15.4%)
3	1 (7.7%)
5	2 (15.4%)
10	1 (7.7%)

3.2.5 Staff

3.2.5.1 Staff dedicated to the triage activity per shift

Nurses

Healthcare assistants

Administrative staff

Security service staff

3.3 General emergency department

3.3.1 Organization

Simultaneous work areas/lines

Organization

Nurses perform some treatments autonomously

All centers
(N=13)

7 (53.8%)

Organization	All centers (N=13)
Structured model of communication for medical handovers	6 (50.0%)
Preprinted forms used	4 (66.7%)
Structured model of communication for nurse handovers	4 (30.8%)
Preprinted forms used	3 (75.0%)
Referent nurse for each shift	10 (76.9%)
Formal protocol for the training of the nurses newly hired in the ED	
Hospital level	8 (88.9%)
Regional/National level	1 (11.1%)
No protocol	0 (0.0%)
Outpatient clinic for low-priority/minor triage codes	5 (38.5%)
Managed by medical ED staff on rotation	2 (40.0%)
Managed by independent contractors with project-based contracts	1 (20.0%)
Managed by general practitioners	2 (40.0%)
Managed by other	0 (0.0%)
RAT	3 (23.1%)
Doctor-to-patient approach	2 (15.4%)

	All centers (N=13)
Shared protocols	
No	3 (23.1%)
Yes	10 (76.9%)

Physicians autonomously manage:

3.3.2 Spaces

Spaces	All centers (N=13)
ED organized as:	
Open space	1 (7.7%)
Outpatient clinic	3 (23.1%)
Mixed	9 (69.2%)
Relax room for the ED staff	11 (91.7%)
Grieving room	6 (46.2%)
Room dedicated to specialist consultant physicians	3 (23.1%)
Room dedicated to gender-based violence	6 (46.2%)
Room dedicated to the communication with relatives	7 (53.8%)
Storage rooms dedicated to the ED	12 (92.3%)
Negative pressure rooms present in the ED	8 (61.5%)
Dedicated pre-examination waiting area	11 (84.6%)
Dedicated post-examination waiting area	4 (30.8%)

3.3.3 Resources and equipment

Equipment	All centers (N=13)
Request exams and receive medical reports with pneumatic mail	5 (38.5%)
Request exams and receive medical reports with ED EHR	12 (92.3%)
Request exams and receive medical reports with other system	0 (0.0%)
Radiology area	10 (76.9%)
Blood cultures processed in the laboratory 24/7	12 (92.3%)
Laptops	6 (46.2%)
Areas that are not directly overseen by ED/hospital staff	7 (53.8%)

Features of the ED EHR

3.3.4 Staff

3.3.4.1 Medical staff

Number of physician per shift (resident physician excluded)

Number of visits per physician each hour

All centers (N=13)

Number of visits per physician each hour

Mean (SD)	2.1 (1.6)
Median (Q1, Q3)	1.6 (0.9, 2.4)
Missing	1

		All centers (N=13)
Resident ED physician available		
No		1 (7.7%)
Yes		12 (92.3%)
Fully autonomous staff		
No		7 (53.8%)
Yes		6 (46.2%)

3.3.4.1.1 ED with fully autonomous staff

		All centers (N=6)
Attending medical staff fully dedicated (percentage)		
Mean (SD)		61.1 (37.6)
Median		66.7
Q1, Q3		58.7, 80.0
Missing		1

3.3.4.1.2 ED with NOT fully autonomous staff

		All centers (N=7)
Weekly hours covered by attending physicians (percentage)		
Mean (SD)		76 (24)
Median (Q1, Q3)		86 (69, 87)
Missing		0
Fully dedicated		
Mean (SD)		67 (34)
Median (Q1, Q3)		76 (42, 95)
Missing		0
Weekly hours covered by surgeons (percentage)		
Mean (SD)		9 (13)
Median (Q1, Q3)		0 (0, 15)
Missing		0
Weekly hours covered by phys. from other hospital dep. on rotation (percentage)		
Mean (SD)		7 (13)
Median (Q1, Q3)		0 (0, 8)
Missing		0
Weekly hours covered by phys. from other hospital dep. as temp. contractors (percentage)		
Mean (SD)		0 (0)
Median (Q1, Q3)		0 (0, 0)
Missing		0
Weekly hours covered by independent contractors (percentage)		
Mean (SD)		3 (6)
Median (Q1, Q3)		0 (0, 5)
Missing		0
Weekly hours covered by phys. hired by private businesses (percentage)		
Mean (SD)		4 (6)
Median (Q1, Q3)		0 (0, 9)
Missing		0

3.3.4.2 Nursing staff

**Nurses dedicated to clinical activity/patient care EXCLUSIVELY
(percentage)**

Mean (SD)	94.8 (12.8)
Median	100.0
Q1, Q3	97.3, 100.0
Missing	1

Nurses per shift

Number of visits per nurse each hour

All centers (N=13)

Number of visits per nurse each hour

Mean (SD)	0.8 (0.4)
Median (Q1, Q3)	0.7 (0.6, 0.9)
Missing	1

3.3.4.3 Other personnel

All centers (N=13)

Healthcare assistants available

No	2 (15.4%)
Yes	11 (84.6%)

3.4 Observation unit

3.4.1 General characteristics

		All centers (N=13)
Observation Unit		
No		1 (7.7%)
Yes		12 (92.3%)

Characteristics		All centers (N=12)
Number of beds		
Mean (SD)		10.5 (6.4)
Median (Q1, Q3)		8.0 (7.5, 11.0)
Missing		1
Structure		
Separate rooms		2 (16.7%)
Open space		10 (83.3%)
Dedicated staff		
No		2 (16.7%)
Yes		10 (83.3%)

3.4.1.1 Attending physicians dedicated to the Observation Unit per shift

Other physicians

Nurses

Healthcare assistants

Services	All centers (N=12)
Dedicated bathrooms/toilets for patients	12 (100.0%)
Isolation room with negative pressure	2 (16.7%)
Infrared thermometers	8 (66.7%)
Termoscanner	2 (16.7%)
Pulse oximeters	12 (100.0%)
Multi-parameter monitors	10 (83.3%)
Blood gas analyzer	6 (50.0%)
Electrocardiographs or other equipment to perform ECGs	12 (100.0%)
Ultrasound machines	11 (91.7%)
Transportable vital parameter monitoring systems	10 (83.3%)

Semi-intensive/high-dependency/intermediate-care treatment	All centers (N=12)
Venturimeters/CPAP systems	5 (41.7%)
Ventilators	4 (33.3%)
Venous cannulation devices	3 (25.0%)
Oxygen delivery systems other than CPAP	5 (41.7%)
CPAP helmets	4 (33.3%)
Dialysis/hemofiltration	0 (0.0%)
At least one semi-intensive treatments	5 (41.7%)

Observation unit used for patients awaiting for hospitalization	All centers (N=12)
No	1 (8.3%)
Yes	11 (91.7%)

3.5 Emergency medicine ward

3.5.1 General characteristics

	All centers (N=13)
Emergency medicine ward	
No	4 (30.8%)
Yes	9 (69.2%)

Characteristics	All centers (N=9)
Number of beds	
Mean (SD)	16.4 (8.7)
Median	13.0
Q1, Q3	12.0, 24.0
Missing	0
Beds with vital parameters monitors (percentage)	
Mean (SD)	60.9 (34.1)
Median	61.5
Q1, Q3	58.3, 83.3
Missing	0
Electronic medical record	7 (87.5%)
CVVH	4 (44.4%)
Average length of stay (days, last year)	
Mean (SD)	6.7 (2.3)
Median	6.2
Q1, Q3	5.0, 7.7
Missing	1
Ward adjacent to the ED	3 (33.3%)
Same staff manage the EMW and the ED	8 (88.9%)

Management	All centers (N=9)
In CPAP/NIV	7 (77.8%)
Treated with vasoactive agents	7 (77.8%)
Polytraumas	7 (77.8%)
Acute coronary syndrome	8 (88.9%)
Gastrointestinal hemorrhage	9 (100.0%)
Hemodynamic instability	9 (100.0%)
Invasive monitoring	2 (22.2%)
Non-surgical polytraumas	7 (77.8%)

ED Software - Technical questionnaire

1. Email *

1. Contact Information

2. 1.1 Hospital or health organization name *

3. 1.2 Contact person's name *

4. 1.3 Contact person's role in the health organizations *

2. Electronic Health Record (EHR) in the Emergency Department

5. 2.1 Is there an EHR in your emergency department (ED)? *

Contrassegna solo un ovale.

Yes *Passa alla domanda 6.*

No *Passa alla domanda 41.*

2.1 details. If there is an EHR in your ED, please answer the following questions:

6. 2.1.1 What is the name and the version of the software? *

7. 2.1.2 What is the name of the software house? *

8. 2.1.3 Please provide the software house contacts

9. 2.1.4 Where is the EHR hosted? Please provide details(e.g. hospital CED servers, cloud, ...) *

10. **2.1.5** The EHR installation serves a single ED or a group of EDs? *

11. **2.1.5.1** If the single installation serves a group of EDs, please list them

12. **2.1.6** Which are the main functionalities and processes provided by the ED EHR: patient admission, triage, clinical evaluation, ... (please list them) *

13. **2.1.7** The observation unit events are registered in the ED EHR or in a separate record? *

Contrassegna solo un ovale.

- Part of ED EHR
- In a separate record

14. **2.1.8** If there is any available technical (i.e. architecture specification, data flow schemas, ...) and functional documentation (i.e. user guide, data dictionary, data model, ...), please upload it

File inviati:

15. **2.1.9** Is there any institutional recommendation in your country about the ED EHR? For example: *

- functionalities that must be present in the software
- data to be collected by the software
- monitoring allowed by the software
- documents to be produced by the software

16. **2.1.10** When the last major update of the ED EHR occurred? *

17. **2.1.11** Is there any plan to replace the ED software in the next 5 years ? *

Contrassegna solo un ovale.

- Yes
- No or not known

18. **2.1.11.1** if yes, when will it be replaced and which software will be the new one (if you already know it)?

3. ED reports repository

19. **3.1** In which format is the ED report EHR document stored? Please provide details (e.g. PDF, xml, ...) *

20. **3.2** Where are the ED report EHR documents stored? Please provide details (e.g. ED EHR file system, ED EHR database, Hospital repository, ...) *

21. **3.3** In which format are the lab test results available in ED? Please provide details (e.g. PDF, structured data, ...) *

22. **3.4** Where are the the lab test results stored? Please provide details (e.g. both in Laboratory Information System and ED EHR, only in LIS, ...) *

23. **3.5** In which format are the radiology test reports available in ED? Please provide details (e.g. PDF, structured data, ...) *

24. **3.6** Where are the laboratory test results stored? Please provide details (e.g. both in Radiology Information System and ED EHR, only in RIS, ...) *

4. Interoperability

25. **4.1** Which kind of data integration solutions does the ED EHR support? e.g. SOAP, REST, EDI, ... (The answer can be "none") *

26. **4.2** Is the ED EHR integrated with other Hospital software? *

Seleziona tutte le voci applicabili.

- a. Radiology information system: tests requests and radiology reports are available in the ED EHR
- b. Laboratory information system: tests requests and laboratory reports are available in the ED EHR
- c. Pre-hospital emergency service system: some data of the pre-hospital (ambulance, 112) record are imported into the ED record
- d. Hospital admission system: the patient's admission code is imported into the ED EHR
- e. None

27. **4.2.1** Possible additional notes to the previous answer

28. **4.3** Is there already any automatized data flow from the ED EHR to other information systems? *

Contrassegna solo un ovale.

Yes

No

29. **4.3.1** If yes, please provide details about:

- List of the main EHR data exchanged
- Frequency of the transmissions
- Integration techniques: e.g. DB view, DB synchronization, web service SOAP, REST, ...
- Format of the exchanged data: e.g. pdf, xml, json, ...

30. **4.4** The EHR feeds an informative monitor for the waiting patient in the ED? Which information does it display (e.g. waiting time, n. of waiting patients for each priority level, ...)? *

31. **4.5** The EHR feeds an informative mobile app/web site for citizens and institutions? Which information do they display (e.g. crowding level, n. of waiting patients, ...)? *

32. **4.6** Is there any current or planned interoperability, involving ED data, that is based on the HL7 FHIR standard, or is there any project in this direction? *

Contrassegna solo un ovale.

Yes, there is a current integration based on the HL7 FHIR standard

No, there aren't any integrations or projects

33. **4.6.1** If yes, please provide details

34. **4.7** Is there some level of FAIRification realized for the ED EHR data collection? *

Contrassegna solo un ovale.

Yes

No

35. **4.7.1** If yes, please provide details about the methods and processes that make your ED EHR data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable?

36. **4.8** Is there a data dictionary available for your ED EHR data collection, that includes the definition, the format, the use of an ontology or classification, value range and controls for each field or for the main ones? *

Contrassegna solo un ovale.

- Yes
 No

37. **4.8.1** If there is any, please upload the documentation

File inviati:

38. **4.9** Have you implemented any process or procedure to ensure data curation/data quality? *

Contrassegna solo un ovale.

- Yes
 No

39. **4.9.1** If yes, please provide details

40. **4.9.2** If yes, please upload any possible documentation

File inviati:

5. Details about data collection

We need to know which data are collected by your ED EHR and are potentially available for being sent to the eCREAM data hub. Please download the excel ([CLICK HERE](#)), fill it and send it to wp2.ecream@astir.com

eCREAM could need data flows from the ED EHR containing these data - are they available?						
DATA	SPECIFICATIONS	AVAILABILITY	TIPOLOGY	FORMAT	Any coding used or organized set of values	Others required
		Answer with an X: YES / NO	Answer with an X: Observed / Free text	Answer with an X: Number / String / Other		
Time of arrival in ED	Time of arrival in ED					
Patient's access identification code	Patient's access identification code					
How the patient arrived at the ED	How the patient arrived at the ED by ambulance, sent by 112, by helicopter, sent by 115, sent by ED of another hospital, by their own means, ...					
Patient access in ED	In case of ED pre-hospital treatment: I12 reception identification code I13 control station that managed the emergency case					
	In case of transfer from another hospital: patient's access identification code in the emergency ED					
	In case of transfer from another hospital: transfer identification code					
	Access time (from triage) time					
	Priority level					
	Minor clinical problems detected during the triage process					
Reassessment of the	Reassessment time					

If you need any clarification, please write to wp2.ecream@astir.com. You can modify your answers even after submitting.

Thank you for your help!

2.1 details. If there is no EHR in your ED, please answer the following questions:

41. **2.1.12** Is there any plan to adopt an ED software in the next 5 years? *

Contrassegna solo un ovale.

- Yes
 No

42. **2.1.13** If yes, when will it be adopted and which software will be (if you already know it)?

If you need any clarification, please write to wp2.ecream@astir.com. You can modify your answers even after submitting.

Thank you for your help!

eCREAM need data flows from the ED EHR containing these data – are they available?

	DATA	SPECIFICATIONS	AVAILABILITY of data			TYPOLOGY of data as collected in the EHR		CODIFICATION, for the codified data (e.g. ICD9CM for diagnosis)	TIME of registration in the EHR	Additional notes
			YES, exactly as specified	YES, but with some difference from the definition: please provide details	Absolutely not	Structured field	Included in free text: please provide details			
Patient access in ED	Patient arrival at the ED	Time of arrival	Date and hour of the patient's arrival at the ED. It could be referred to the reception or administrative acceptance							
		Patient's access identification code	Unique identifier of the ED admission							
		Arrival mode/pathway	How the patient arrived at the ED: e.g. by ambulance dispatched by pre-hospital emergency service (EMS), by helicopter dispatched by EMS, transferred from an ED of another Hospital, Self-presented/by their own means, ...							
		Dispatcher	E.g.: Pre-hospital emergency service, sending Hospital, GP, ...							
		Pre-hospital mission code (in case of arrival by ambulance/helicopter)	It is the unique identification code for that single mission							
		Pre-hospital emergency service Operations Center (in case of arrival by ambulance/helicopter)	Identification code of the Operations Center that managed the mission							
		In case of transfer from another Hospital: Patient's access identification code in the previous ED	Corresponds to the ED acceptance code assigned in the Hospital that has requested the patient's transfer							
In case of transfer from another Hospital: Sending Hospital	Corresponds to the name/code of the Hospital that requested the patient's transfer									
Triage	Triage	Triage time	Date and hour							
		Priority level	Priority level code assigned to the patient				1,2,3,4,5			
Re-evaluation	Re-evaluation of the priority level	Main clinical problem and symptoms detected during the triage evaluation	list of problems/symptoms							
		Re-evaluation time	Date and hour of the re-evaluation of the patient's triage/priority level							
Time-dependent disease	Time-dependent disease	New priority level	Priority level code assigned to the patient							
		Time of assessment	When it was established that the patient was to be treated following a specific time-dependent disease protocol							
Time-dependent disease	Time-dependent disease	Time-dependent disease	Which time-dependent disease was detected: e.g Stroke, MI, Major Trauma, ...							
		ED treatment area	In which ED area the patient is treated (e.g. high intensity care area, shock room, ...)							
Treatment	Treatment	Time of nurse initiated treatment	Date and hour when the nurses starts their treatment							
		Nurse identification code	Nurse's identification code in the ED organization							
		Time of the visit performed by the physician	Date and hour							
		Physician identification code	Physician's identification code in the ED organization							
	Laboratory tests list	Type	Laboratory test type / codification							
		Request time	Laboratory test request - date and hour							
		Execution time	Laboratory test execution - date and hour							
		Time of results availability in ED	Laboratory test results availability in ED - date and hour							
	Radiology exams	Results	Test results							
		Type	Radiology test type / codification					ICD9CM		
		Request time	Radiology test request - date and hour							
		Execution time	Radiology test execution - date and hour							
	Specialist consultancy	Time of report availability in ED	Radiology test results availability in ED - date and hour							
		Results	Report written by the clinician/radiologist							
Type		Speciality								
Request time		Specialist consultancy request - date and hour								
Procedures (specific surgical, medical, or diagnostic interventions)	Execution time	Specialist consultancy execution - date and hour								
	Time of report availability in ED	Specialist consultancy results availability in ED - date and hour								
	Results	Report written by the specialist								
	Type	Procedure type								
Pharmaceutical therapy	Request time	Procedure request - date and hour								
	Execution time	Procedure execution - date and hour								
Respiratory support	Therapy	Therapy type					ATC			
	Time of prescription	Pharmaceutical therapy prescription - date and hour								
Vital signs monitoring	Time of administration	Pharmaceutical therapy administration - date and hour								
	Start time	Respiratory support start date and hour								
Discharge decision	Discharge decision	End time	Respiratory support end date and hour							
		Start time	Vital signs monitoring start date and hour							
Discharge decision	Discharge decision	End time	Vital signs monitoring end date and hour							
		Time of discharge decision	Date and hour when the physician identifies the best outcome of treatment. It does not correspond to the discharge time, if the patient has to wait for a bed or a transfer to another hospital (boarding)							
Discharge decision	Discharge decision	Expected outcome	Expected treatment outcome, e.g. home, hospitalization, transfer, ED observation unit ...							
		Type of hospital admission unit/department, in case of planned hospitalization	Ordinary, semi-intensive or intensive bed							
Discharge decision	Discharge decision	Destination hospital, in case of planned transfer	Name/code of the destination hospital							

